

Priority-Based Opportunistic Computation Offloading For Multi-User In Edge IoT Environment

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of smart city infrastructures and industrial IoT (IIoT) applications have intensified the demand for intelligent computation offloading strategies capable of adapting to dynamic wireless conditions, heterogeneous task characteristics, and diverse Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements. Traditional offloading approaches often employ fixed and discrete offloading strategies, which limit flexibility and result in sub-optimal energy-delay performance. Consequently, IIoT applications generate tasks of varying urgency, ranging from real-time traffic monitoring to emergency collision detection. However, traditional models often considered all tasks equal without incurring task urgency. To overcome these limitations, Priority-Sorted based Opportunistic Computation Offloading (PSCO) algorithm is proposed. It is built on actor-critic deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG) algorithm, which incorporates mixed offloading, allowing each task to decide the optimal proportion of data processed locally and the proportion executed at the MEC. To further enhance efficiency of the system, tasks are assigned priority levels reflecting their urgency such as high priority public safety alerts, medium-priority traffic flow updates and low priority ambient sensing. The actor network learns continuous offloading ratios for task prioritization execution efficiently, while the critic estimates long-term performance estimation parameters such as delay and energy consumption. Furthermore, priority-weighted delay is introduced ensuring high priority tasks is embedded into the reward function to enforce stricter penalties. Simulation results demonstrate the PSCO algorithm outperforms baseline DDQN algorithm by 12–15% reduction in terms of average delay and 40% increase in terms of offloading decision efficiency. The combination of mixed offloading and priority-aware optimization significantly enhances task prioritization and offloading decision efficiency for heterogeneous IIoT applications operating in dynamic edge computing environments.

Keywords: Edge IoT, Deep Priority- Deterministic Policy Gradient, Computation Offloading

Introduction

An extensive network of linked devices that provide constant streams of data has been brought about by the Internet of Things' (IoT) explosive growth [1]. Complex computational processes are difficult to conduct locally on these devices due to their frequently restricted computer power, energy capacity, and storage. Conventional cloud infrastructure, which uses a centralized way to deliver more computer resources, has been used to alleviate this limitation. Nevertheless, in real-time sensing applications, the enormous amount of data produced by IoT devices needs to be transferred to the cloud, which might result in severe network congestion and higher latency. Applications where quick data processing is crucial, such as driverless cars, industrial automation, and healthcare monitoring, cannot tolerate such delays [2]. Due to these constraints, Edge computing (EC) has emerged as a concept that places servers near endpoints to expand cloud computing capabilities to the network edge. By facilitating low-latency task offloading, EC eases the burden on IoT devices and enhances system performance overall [3]. Mobile users, edge clouds with virtual machines (VMs), and distant cloud infrastructures located in data centers make up a typical MEC scenario, as shown in Figure 1. In order to create multi-server systems and deliver a range of services to mobile consumers, edge cloud service providers rent virtual machines (VMs) from edge clouds. Users pay costs depending on the amount and quality of services rendered after submitting service requests, and they get processed results in line with a predetermined service-level agreement (SLA). SLAs provide quality of service (QoS) metrics such as response time, task waiting probability, and average number of tasks in multi-server systems, formalizing the rights and obligations of mobile users and service providers [4]. With its flexibility in using compute and bandwidth from and between each layer, EC is a good fit and is done by computation offloading [5]. According to [6] the services provided by Google, Facebook are deployed on edge servers, which results in improved Quality of Services (QoS) by optimizing energy, communication overhead using data partitioning.

Figure 1 MEC Scenario

Computation offloading is an essential strategy in an edge-enabled IoT ecosystem, where tasks generated by IoT devices can be executed locally or sent to adjacent MEC servers[7]. It can enhance user computing performance while extending the terminal device's service cycle and battery life [8]. Determining whether the task offloading technique is cost-effective for the user equipment in terms of energy consumption and execution latency is often the goal of decision-making. This technique creates a balance between the local device and the server, which is done using data partitioning. The process of offloading results in less computing and high communication[9]. According to the process of computation offloading, there are four major steps, which include the most suitable technique for computation offloading by considering various parameters like task sensitivity, mobile device, and server capabilities. The second step is to check the resource availability and allocate the resources to each user. In the third step, for dynamic scenarios, provide uninterrupted service delivery even when there is mobility from the user end. Lastly, there are real-time system updates, which adapt to the dynamic changes that occur in the environment.

Primarily, there are two offloading techniques, which are partial offloading, which is the decentralization of tasks in such a way that only a portion of data is computed on the local device, and the remaining goes to the server[10]. Second, offloading binary offloading in which either the task is computed on the local device or it is fully computed on the server [11]. The only objective of these computation offloading techniques is to relate to mobile devices (LDs) energy consumption and latency of the task[12]. According to [13], there will be 75 billion smart devices in use by 2025, and that the volume of data produced by these devices would rise to an astounding 2.3 zettabytes annually, compared to the 1.1 zettabytes per year forecast in 2016, which may result a challenging situation for offloading. Additionally, the wireless resource allocation method, which is influenced by power control and interference management schemes, is a major factor in the compute offloading strategy's energy efficiency. Consequently, it is imprudent to focus solely on considering one offloading strategy. Therefore, it adopts an opportunistic computation offloading strategy [14]. In edge-IoT environments, opportunistic computational offloading refers to adaptive decision procedures that take advantage of transient network, device, and edge-server conditions to decide whether, when, and how much of a task should be carried out locally or remotely[15]. Depending on the current system state and long-term performance goals, opportunistic strategies choose full offload, no offload, or fractional (partitioned) offload actions. This unifies binary and partial offloading in highly dynamic industrial IoT settings with fluctuating channel quality, time-varying workload arrivals, and heterogeneous device energy constraints.[16]. The main objective in an Edge IoT environment is to provide a good quality-of-service (QoS) in dynamic conditions, hence requiring an autonomous and efficient offloading strategy.

Recent advancement in artificial intelligence gives a solution to the problem, that is, integration of reinforcement learning(RL) with deep neural networks, hence called deep reinforcement learning(DRL)[17]. This allows autonomous intelligent making and optimization of tasks, according to the dynamic conditions of the Edge IoT environment. This helps in load balancing and dynamically adjusting workloads according to channel conditions[18]. As suggested by [6], a framework for offloading that is optimized for delays in mobile edge computing for IIoT systems with multiple users. By introducing partial offloading, it makes it possible to distribute duties between MEC servers and local devices. Additionally, it uses DDPG and Q-learning algorithms to adaptively determine offloading ratios under different network and channel conditions. [19] provides a framework for DRL to maximize task offloading in time-varying MEC environments. The offloading issue is modeled as a Markov Decision Process, in which an agent makes dynamic decisions about transmission power and task allocation depending on server load, task size, and channel conditions. In comparison to conventional heuristics, the suggested approach uses a deep deterministic policy gradient(DDPG)-based algorithm to achieve continuous and adaptive control while lowering latency and energy usage. The model's efficacy for dynamic MEC scenarios is validated by simulation results, which show increased system stability and efficiency under varying network conditions. Prior studies disregard the fact that the compute tasks have varying levels of value for users, assuming that all activities are equally significant. For instance, security activities (like car and road detection) are given top priority in LDs, followed by real-time tasks (like games and AR/VR) and non-real-time tasks (like user behavior analysis tasks). Furthermore, when addressing the optimal offloading problem, the queue waiting and

execution time on the MEC servers should also be taken into account. Priority-based activities and resource-constrained MEC servers necessitate a high-performance computation offloading technique[20].

In the rapidly evolving landscape of MEC, task offloading plays a crucial role in enhancing computational efficiency and reducing latency for IoT applications. Hence, the shortcomings in the Edge IoT environment are: Need for Adaptability: Edge IoT environments vary significantly in terms of network topology, resource availability, application requirements, and user demands. There is a need for adaptable and flexible optimisation methods that can be customised to different edge IoT environments and use cases [14]. Assumption of Equal Importance for All Tasks: Many existing offloading schemes assume that all computation tasks generated by mobile devices are equally important. This means that the same level of computational resources and priority is given to each task, regardless of its actual importance to the user [21]. Queue Waiting and Execution Delays on MEC Servers: When tasks are offloaded to MEC servers, they often enter a queue to be processed. The time a task spends waiting in the queue and the time it takes to be executed can significantly impact the overall performance, particularly for high-priority tasks. Developing an offloading scheme in scenarios where different types of tasks coexist, each with varying levels of importance, is crucial. By prioritizing the tasks based on their importance and optimized resource usage, the system can ensure that critical tasks are completed on time, improving the overall performance and reliability of MEC in IoT networks [20]. Hence, there need for priority-based joint optimization and intelligent autonomous techniques, for resource allocation and offloading system for delay-sensitive applications in a multiuser Edge-IoT(MIoT) system.

1.1 Proposed Methodology

We propose a priority-based opportunistic computation offloading method for a multi-user Edge IoT (MIoT) environment aligned with the operational demands of Industry 4.0 smart city applications. The system processes multiple user tasks simultaneously, with each task capable of being executed locally on the IoT device or externally at the MEC server. To determine the optimal offloading behaviour, a Priority-Sorted Opportunistic Computation Offloading (PSCO) algorithm is introduced, featuring an actor-critic architecture that learns a continuous and adaptive offloading ratio for each user.

Conventional offloading approaches typically depend on a fixed or discrete offloading ratio, limiting their ability to handle fluctuating wireless conditions, diverse computing loads, and varying service urgency. In contrast, the actor network in PSCO produces a continuous mixed-offloading action representing a fusion of full and partial offloading thereby enabling each task to split its execution dynamically based on channel gain, device capacity, and MEC conditions. The critic network evaluates the quality of these offloading decisions across high-dimensional state-action spaces, overcoming the constraints of reinforcement learning.

To incorporate QoS differentiation, each task is assigned a priority level $P_l \in \{1,2,3\}$, corresponding to high, medium, and low urgency. Lower numerical values represent latency-critical tasks typical in smart city environments such as emergency response analytics or real-time traffic monitoring. Priority affects the learning process through a priority-weighted delay term $\frac{1}{P_l}$, ensuring that high-priority tasks impose larger penalties when delayed. This mechanism guides the learning model to allocate more computation and communication resources to tasks requiring faster turnaround, ultimately improving responsiveness under resource-constrained conditions.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- **Priority Based Decision Making**
Task are sorted in high, medium or low priority values, which directly influence delay penalties during learning . This ensures that delay-sensitive tasks receive the highest priority and have preferential access to MEC resources. In smart-city scenarios, there are critical task like emergency alerts which requires urgent response as compared to low priority task like data transfer. By incorporating, priority-weighted delay, the system learns to reduce the delay of critical tasks without degrading overall system performance.
- **Adaptive Opportunistic Offloading Policy**
A continuous opportunistic offloading is adopted that allows a fusion of partial and binary offloading for improved adaptability in dynamic conditions. Unlike the conventional methods, this offloading technique provides greater flexibility under various wireless conditions, reduced execution delay and provide balance device load, resulting improved QoS.
- **Continuous Decision Model For Dynamic Offloading**
We construct an actor-critic reinforcement learning architecture with clearly defined state, action, and reward functions to learn optimal offloading ratios under continuous action space. Unlike fixed-ratio or Q-table-based offloading approaches, the proposed DDPG model can adaptively tune the offloading level according to variations in channel conditions, workload intensity, and MEC queue length. This is necessary because static or discrete offloading rules fail to cope with the fluctuating wireless and computation environment typical of large-scale smart-city deployments.
- **Joint Optimization Of Delay, Energy Consumption And Priority-Weighted Rewards**
The reward function integrates total execution delay, energy consumption and priority-weighted delay to guide the learning algorithm toward efficient and QoS-aware decisions. This combination is essential because smart-city IoT

devices operate under strict energy constraints while also requiring timely execution of high-priority task. The joint objectives ensure a balanced improvement in responsiveness, energy efficiency and overall system stability.

1.2. Related works

Over the years, many researchers have contributed to computation offloading using MEC. Techniques like Deep Reinforcement Learning(DRL), heuristic optimization, and queueing theory, etc., were discussed that emphasize minimizing latency, lowering energy consumption, and optimizing resource allocation[22][23][24]

In recent years, deep learning and edge computing have both advanced quickly and shown significant success in their respective domains. To completely realize the underlying potential of big data and meet the constantly rising needs of diverse applications, however, the enormous volume of priceless data created and gathered at the edge necessitates the localization of more potent and intelligent processing capabilities. Thankfully, recent advances in deep learning have illuminated the edge application situations, offering robust capabilities in domains like as data management, information perception, and decision-making. When these two technologies come together, it can open up even more possibilities and enable the creation of several new applications. To accomplish edge computing, artificial intelligence (AI) has already been progressively incorporated with edge computing. Further combining deep learning (DL) and reinforcement learning (RL) results in deep reinforcement learning (DRL). By interacting with the environment, it seeks to create an agent that can learn the optimal course of action across a range of states in order to optimize the cumulative long-term benefits[25].

There is a common trend seen in the survey, which is optimization for minimization of energy and delay. In [26] proposed a mixed integer problem, to minimize the delay and energy consumption by optimizing the offloading decision and local CPU. In an edge computing context,[27] provided an efficient method for the effective use of power for IoT hardware components. Predicting and managing the periods of inactivity of Internet of Things devices by using balanced battery power and associated historical usefulness. In the edge cloud computing environment, [28] created a strategy based on the double DQN to improve resource allocation for compute-intensive and delay-sensitive applications. Our plan decides what should be done in the present system state to improve the edge cloud's overall performance. [29] Suggest an online-offline learning approach to ascertain the MEC policy for every work that is completed. In particular, first train offline energy and delay estimators that forecast the predicted energy and delay, respectively, for completing a job at a particular edge server. An RL agent that has been taught online, then uses the trained estimator to develop an MEC policy in real time. Develop a Multi-Queue Priority scheduling algorithm (MQP) in [30]that prioritizes task completion time for both the generator and the executor. In order to reduce scheduling delay, this technique converts successive offloading procedures into queue updates. It does this with little cost and complexity. An intelligent joint optimization approach for resource allocation and compute offloading in pervasive edge IoT systems that is powered by DRL was provided by[14]. Decisions on offloading, resource allocation, and relay selection are all dependent on CDS. By limiting the CPU, bandwidth, and power, they frame the combined optimization approach for compute offloading and resource allocation into a MINP problem in order to minimize the system's overall energy consumption and latency. This is the first time that a CDS-based relay has been used. Some more literature surveysare described in Table 1.

Table 1 Literature Survey on Computation Offloading

	Optimization technique	Algorithm	Priority	Key Metrics
[31]	Resource allocation and continuous control	DDPG	No	Delay , convergence
[32]	Transmission power and privacy	COPP-DDPG	Yes	Delay, Throughput
[33]	Resource allocation	DRL	Yes	Complexity
[34]	Discrete offloading	DDQN	No	Energy
[35]	Multi-objective DRL	DDPG	No	Delay
[36]	Continuous offloading	DDPG	Yes	Delay, Energy
[37]	Resource Allocation	DQN	No	Latency
[38]	Discrete-continuous offloading	DDPG	Yes	Energy, Delay
[39]	Resource Allocation	DDPG	No	Latency
	Optimization technique	Algorithm	Priority	Key Metrics

[1]	Resource allocation and continuous control	DDPG	No	Delay , convergence
[2]	Transmission power and privacy	COPP-DDPG	Yes	Delay, Throughput
[3]	Resource allocation	DRL	Yes	Complexity
[4]	Discrete offloading	DDQN	No	Energy
[5]	Multi-objective DRL	DDPG	No	Delay
[6]	Continuous offloading	DDPG	Yes	Delay, Energy
[7]	Resource Allocation	DQN	No	Latency
[8]	Discrete-continuous offloading	DDPG	Yes	Energy, Delay
[9]	Resource Allocation	DDPG	No	Latency

2.1 Proposed Methodology

A priority-based MEC system intended for settings where tasks produced by end devices vary in both their computing needs and priority levels, a set of MIIoT devices, which is K , is listed $1,2,3 \dots K$. A Task is generated by each device based on the quantity of the incoming data and the number of CPU cycles c needed to complete it at time step t . A single MEC server in the system is considered in the system model, as shown in Figure 2, along with different types of tasks and nomenclature used in the paper is described in Table 2. For a particular user i , T define the input data size, which is then pre-processed into a discrete priority level p_i (low, medium, or high) to indicate its importance in industrial processes. Tasks can be performed locally by devices or partially or totally offloaded to a nearby MEC server with constrained processing power. This section presents a mathematical methodology for priority based opportunistic offloading in MIIoT environment. The formulation follows a structured mathematical workflow, in which each equation depends upon another to set up the foundation of proposed priority based opportunistic offloading(PSCO) algorithm, with the objective of minimization of delay and energy under dynamic conditions.

Table 2 : Symbols used along with its description

Symbol	Description
K	Number of IoT users/devices
i	Index of IoT user ($i = 1, 2, \dots, K$)
t	Time slot index
T_i	Input task size for user i (in bits)
$a_i \in [0,1]$	Offloading ratio for user i ($1 =$ full offload, $0 =$ local, $0 < a < 1 =$ partial/mixed offload)
$L_i^{off} = a_i \cdot T_i$	Task portion offloaded to the MEC server
$L_i^{loc} = (1 - a_i) \cdot T_i$	Task portion executed locally
c_i	Required CPU cycles per bit for task of user i
h_i	Wireless channel gain for user i
B	Available wireless bandwidth (Hz)
P_i	Transmission power of user i
N_0	Noise power spectral density
$SINR_i$	Signal-to-noise ratio of user i
R_i	Achievable uplink transmission rate of user i
D_i^{trans}	Transmission delay for offloaded data (<i>uplink</i>)
D_i^{loc}	Local computation delay
D_i^{mec}	MEC computation delay
D_i	Total delay for user i 's task
E_i^{loc}	Local computation energy consumption
E_i^{trans}	Transmission energy consumption
E_i	Total energy consumed by user i
f_i^{loc}	Local CPU frequency allocated to user i
f_i^s	MEC CPU frequency allocated to user i

f_{\max}	Maximum CPU capacity of MEC server
$f_i^{\text{loc}_{\max}}$	Maximum local CPU frequency for device i
$Q_s(t)$	MEC task queue length (in CPU cycles) at time t
p_i	Priority level of task for user i : 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low
w_i	Priority weight for user i (e.g., 3 for high, 2 for medium, 1 for low)
$D_i^w = w_i \cdot D_i$	Priority-weighted delay
λ	Weight factor balancing delay and energy in reward/cost function
α	Priority penalty coefficient (only in Algorithm 2)
r	Instantaneous reward for RL agent
γ	Discount factor for DRL
$\pi(\cdot)$	Actor network policy mapping state \rightarrow action
$Q(\cdot)$	Critic network estimating state-action value
s_t	Environment state at time t
a_t	Action vector at time t (offloading decisions for all users)
ρ	Target network soft update rate
\mathfrak{B}	Replay buffer for DRL
Δ_i	Deadline or maximum tolerable delay for user i
β	Penalty term for violating delay constraints
η	Exploration noise (actor network)
r_{imax}	Maximum offloading ratio (normally 1.0)
F_i^{share}	MEC CPU share allocated to user i (priority-weighted)
σ^2	Noise variance

Figure 2 System Model

2.2 Wireless Communication Model

To characterize uplink performance, the wireless channel is modelled using signal to interference noise ratio (SINR). (Eqn 1) measures how strong the user's signal is compared to noise and interference. This eqn depends upon, per-user effective bandwidth allocation \tilde{B}_i depends on the resource sharing scheme. According to equal-bandwidth allocation $\tilde{B}_i = \frac{W}{r_k}$, where $r_k = \{i: a_i > 0\}$ is number of offloading users. $\tilde{B}_i \approx \text{tmp}_{rn} = W \times 10^3 / r_k \times 10^3$. Linear transmit power P in Watts is described as $P = p_i \cdot 10^{-3}$ (if p_i in mW). Pathloss model used is $L_i = d_i^{-3}$ which records signal attenuation at a distance, while assuming cubic decay. Noise power in the allocated bandwidth is $\mathcal{N}_i = \tilde{B}_i \cdot N_0$, where N_0 denotes thermal noise density. Then the signal to noise ratio (SINR) is

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{P L_i}{\mathcal{N}_i} = \frac{p_i \cdot 10^{-3} d_i^{-3}}{\tilde{B}_i N_0} \quad (1)$$

Computing achievable data rate Eqn 1 applies Shannon's capacity formula. For According to Shannon rate (bits/sec) for user i , the attainable data rate is r_i , this rate indicates the maximum transmission throughput available for a user at any time t , acting as the foundation of all opportunistic offloading decisions. This determines the maximum theoretical rate in bits per second that may be achieved in the presence of Gaussian noise.

$$r_i = \tilde{B}_i \log_2 (1 + \text{SINR}_i) \quad (2)$$

2.2 Transmission delay

Transmission delay measures how long it takes for a user to send task data to the MEC server. It is the offloaded portion of the task is transmitted over the wireless link. **Eqn 3** computes the transmission delay as a function of the fraction of task offloaded, size of offloaded data, achievable wireless rate from **Eqn 2**. If D_i is given in kilobytes (KB) and r_i in bits/sec, converting bytes from bits with factor 8. therefore, the transmission delay for user i , is described as:

$$t_i^{tx} = \frac{\alpha_i D_i \cdot 8}{r_i} \quad (3)$$

where α_i is the offloading decision for each user j , the fraction of task offloaded is denoted by $\alpha_i \in [0,1]$

$\alpha_i = 1$ Full offloading

$\alpha_i = 0$ Local offloading

$0 < \alpha_i < 1$ = Partial offloading

For example there are 5 users with offloading decision so $a=[0,0,0,0,1,0,0,0,1,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0]$ then where the computing is done is determined by $V_o = I[0,0=0]+I[0,0=0]+I[1,0>0]+I[0,5>0]+I[0,0=0]=0++1+1+0$, so two users are offloaded and there is equal distribution of B . The delay depends on various factors like data size, allocated bandwidth rate and channel conditions.

This metric reflects the communication cost and strongly influences whether offloading is beneficial for a task based on its priority. This also depict when rate is low, task is computed locally.

2.3 Local Computation Model

The number of CPU cycles required for local computation. Eqn 4 describes how much computation task is computed locally and depends on $(1 - \alpha_i(t))$ that is task which is computed on the local device. $A_i(t)$ is the input data size and c_i shows the CPU cycles per bits required for computation.

$$C_i^{loc}(t) = (1 - \alpha_i(t))A_i(t)c_i. \quad (4)$$

If the CPU frequency allocated to user i is $f_i(t)$. According to **Eqn 5** it computes the local computation delay based on CPU cycles and allocated CPU frequency. It is ratio of number of CPU cycles required for local computation with respect to allocated CPU frequency.

$$D_i^{loc}(t) = \frac{C_i^{loc}(t)}{f_i(t)} \quad (5)$$

Using the dynamic power model that is required for local energy consumption.

$$E_i^{loc}(t) = \kappa_i f_i^2(t) D_i^{loc}(t) = \kappa_i (1 - \alpha_i(t)) A_i(t) c_i f_i(t) \quad (6)$$

where κ_i is the effective switched capacitance coefficient, which depicts the processor's energy efficiency. It also signifies that dependence of energy consumption on CPU frequency. These eqns' quantify the resource usage and cost of computing

2.4 MEC Computation Model

In this model the uploaded task portion is transmitted and processed at the MEC server. When a fraction $\alpha_i(t)$ is offloaded to edge server s , the transmission rate over wireless channel $h_{i,s}(t)$ to server s of the offloaded part is depicted in **Eqn 7**

$$R_{i,s}(t) = B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_i(t) h_{i,s}(t)}{N_0} \right) \quad (7)$$

here B is the allocated wireless channel bandwidth, $P_i(t)$ is the transmit power, N_0 is the noise power spectral density. $h_{i,s}(t)$ is the immediate channel gain. Similar to **Eqn 3**, **Eqn 8** is the time required to upload the offloaded portion of the task data from user to MEC server over the wireless channel.

$$D_i^{tx}(t) = \frac{\alpha_i(t) A_i(t)}{R_{i,s}(t)} \quad (8)$$

According to **Eqn 9** measures the energy cost incurred by the user device when transmitting offloaded data to the MEC server.

$$E_i^{tx}(t) = P_i(t)D_i^{tx}(t) \quad (9)$$

Both communication delay and energy cost related to data offloading is captured by these components

Once at the MEC server

According to **Eqn 10**, it is the CPU cycles needed for MEC execution. When the data reaches the edge server, it undergoes execution using the allocated computational resource. At the server s , the required CPU cycles for edge execution are

$$C_{i,s}^{edge}(t) = \alpha_i(t)A_i(t)c_i \quad (10)$$

According to **Eqn 11**, if $f_{u,s}(t)$ is the CPU frequency allocated to user u at server s , the edge computation delay is

$$D_{i,s}^{edge}(t) = \frac{C_{i,s}^{edge}(t)}{f_{i,s}(t)} \quad (11)$$

Overall MEC capacity is restricted by the maximum processing power F_s^{max} , so the total edge server capacity constraint is: defined in **Eqn 12**, that ensures total allocated CPU frequencies that don't exceed the MEC server's processing limit.

$$\sum_{i \in I} f_{i,s}(t) \leq F_s^{max}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (12)$$

By preventing server overload, this constraint guarantees equitable resource distribution among users, also this model captures the interplau between communication delay, server load, processing time.

2.5 Task Completion Delay and Energy

To understand overall execution performance of system total execution delay and total energy consumption is calculated. The total execution delay of user i 's task in slot t is the summation of Eqn 5 which is local processing, Eqn 8 which is transmission processing and Eqn 11 which is edge computation delay. Since local and offloaded portions run simultaneously, the total delay is the maximum of their completion times

$$D_i(t) = \max\{D_i^{loc}(t), D_i^{tx}(t) + D_{i,s}^{edge}(t)\} \quad (13)$$

Indicating which local and offloading paths are longer as a result of concurrent computation. Both **Eqn 6** (local) and **Eqn 9** (transmission) energies are integrated into **Eqn 14** :

$$E_i(t) = E_i^{loc}(t) + E_i^{tx}(t) \quad (14)$$

The two primary objectives that is minimized is **Eqn 13** and **Eqn 14**.

2.6 Optimization Problem

As long as system-level limitations like CPU capacity and transmit power are met, the MEC system's main goal is to reduce the weighted sum of task delay (Eqn 13) and energy consumption (Eqn 14) for every user. Eqn 15 defines the objective function as a weighted sum of delay and energy, where weights incorporate task priority, ensuring high priority tasks receive faster processing and low priority tasks receive partial offloading during congestion.

$$\min_{\alpha_i(t), f_{i,s}(t), P_i(t), f_i(t)} (d_i(t)D_i(t) + \lambda E_i(t)) \quad (15)$$

$$\text{Subjected to :} \quad 0 \leq \alpha_i(t) \leq 1, \quad (15 A)$$

$$0 \leq f_{i,s}(t) \leq 1, \quad (15 B)$$

$$0 \leq P_i(t) \leq P_i^{max} \quad (15 C)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} f_{i,s}(t) \leq F_s^{max} \quad (15 D)$$

Here, F_i^{\max} and F_s^{\max} represents the maximum computation processing capacity of the user device and the MEC server, respectively, while P_i^{\max} represents the maximum limit for each user's transmit power. **Eqn (15 A)** depicts the offloading ratio, that is how much data must be computed on local device and edge side, **Eqn(15 B)** is local device computing capacity, **(Eqn 15 C)** the server capacity and **(Eqn 15 D)** is the transmit power constraints.

The complex coupling between the communication and computation domains is captured by this non-convex optimization problem. The offloading ratio $\alpha_u(t)$, CPU frequency allocation $f_u(t)$, and transmission power $P_u(t)$ are interdependent, making the problem intractable for conventional convex optimization methods.

2.7 Proposed Algorithm for Optimized Offloading

The resource allocation and computation offloading in the MIoT environment is formulated as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), where a discrete time slot t is associated with each decision epoch. The environment state varies at each time step based on the channel conditions, **Eqn 1, Eqn 2**, task arrivals, and CPU allocations according to **Eqn 5, Eqn 6, Eqn 11**. The state space, action space, state transition, and reward function are the four main elements that make up the MDP, as shown in Figure 3.

- **State**

All observable parameters that affect the choices about offloading and resource allocation are included in the state space. The system state at time t is represented as follows for a specific user u and server s :

$$s_t = (Q_i(t), h_{i,s}(t), A_i(t), f_i(t), P_i(t))_{i \in I, s \in S} \quad (16)$$

where $Q_i(t)$, represents the backlog of unprocessed tasks that is length of the local task queue. $h_{i,s}(t)$ denotes the channel gain between user i and the MEC server s , capturing the dynamics of wireless communication. $A_i(t)$ it the newly arrived data of particular user i at time slot t . $f_i(t)$, is the allotted CPU-Cycle frequency for local task computation. $P_i(t)$ is the transmit power used by user i for offloading, these factors are calculated from **Eqn 1 -Eqn 11**. The system is fully represented by this state vector, which allows the learning agent to dynamically accumulate communication and computation conditions.

- **Action**

It defines the set of all possible actions available for each user, that includes resource allocation parameters and offloading decisions:

$$a_t = (\alpha_i(t), f_i(t), P_i(t), f_{i,s}(t))_{i,s} \quad (17)$$

where, $\alpha_i(t)$ is the offloading ratio, $f_i(t)$ is the CPU frequency for local computation, which controls local processing speed and energy consumption. $P_i(t)$ depicts the uplink rate and energy cost. $f_{i,s}(t)$ shows the allocated computation resource by server s to user i . Together, these actions balance latency and energy efficiency by deciding how computation tasks are split between the edge server and local device

- **Reward**

In order to minimize the total cost of the system, including both delay and energy consumption, the reward function is intended to direct the learning process. It is expressed as follows.

$$r_t = - \sum_{i \in I} (d_i(t)D_i(t) + \lambda E_i(t)) \quad (18)$$

$D_i(t)$ depicts the total delay experienced by user i depicted in **Eqn 13**, which consist if transmission delay and computation delay. $E_i(t)$ is the overall energy consumption in **Eqn 14**, depicts during transmission and task execution. $d_i(t)$ depicts the priority weight assigned to user i . λ is the trade-off factor that balances the energy consumption and delay in the reward computation. The reinforcement learning agent will learn to optimize latency and energy consumption simultaneously while taking user priorities into account because of to this negative weighted sum structure.

Figure 3 Algorithm Design

2.8.1 Algorithm Design

Algorithm 1 which is priority-sorted based opportunistic computation offloading(PSCO) , integrates DRL based offloading which is opportunistic computation offloading. Unlike, existing priority based offloading[11],uses fixed priority rules and ignores channel variability.PSCO first sort task by urgency and then opportunistically offload based on wireless rate,CPU demand and MEC availability.Figure 4 shows how algorithm makes the optimal offloading decision using actor-critic method.

Algorithm 1:Priority-Sorted Based Opportunistic Computation Offloading (PSCO)

Input:

- N : Number of user devices
- C_n : Required CPU cycles per task for user n
- P_n : Priority level of task for user n (1 = High, 3 = Low)
- h_n : Channel gain between user n and the base station
- f_{loc} : Local CPU frequency of user device
- f_{edge} : Edge server CPU frequency
- θ : Offloading threshold factor

Output:

- Total execution delay T_{total}
- Priority-weighted delay $T_{weighted}$

Algorithm Steps:

1. **Initialization:**
Set $T_{total} = 0, T_{weighted} = 0$.
Obtain $\{C_n, P_n, h_n\}_{n=1}^N$ for all users.
2. **Task Sorting:**
Sort all tasks in ascending order of P_n (i.e., high priority first).
If two tasks have equal priority, sort them in descending order of C_n .
3. **Offloading Decision:**
For each user $n = 1$ to N :
 - a. Compute local execution delay:
$$T_{loc} = \frac{C_n}{f_{loc}}$$
 - b. Compute edge (offloaded) delay:
$$T_{edge} = \frac{C_n}{f_{edge} \cdot h_n}$$
 - c. **Decision Rule:**
If $T_{edge} < T_{loc} \times (1 + \theta)$, then **offload** task n ;
Else, execute task n **locally**.
4. **Initialize:**
 1. Task queues $Q_u(0) = 0$, neural network parameters for **actor** $\mu_\theta(s)$ and **critic** $Q_\phi(s, a)$, target networks $\mu_{\theta'}, Q_{\phi'}$
 2. Replay buffer $\mathcal{D} = \emptyset$
5. **For each time slot $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$:**
 - a. **Observe system state:**

$$s_t = (Q_u(t), A_u(t), h_{u,s}(t))_{u,s}$$

b. **Select action using actor + exploration noise:**

$$a_t = \mu_\theta(s_t) + \mathcal{N}_t$$

where a_t contains:

1. Offloading ratios $\alpha_u(t)$
2. Local CPU allocation $f_u(t)$
3. Transmit power $P_u(t)$
4. Edge CPU allocation $f_{u,s}(t)$

c. **Compute transmission and computation delays** for all users u :

$$D_u^{tx}(t) = \frac{\alpha_u(t)A_u(t)}{R_{u,s}(t)}, D_u^{loc}(t) = \frac{(1 - \alpha_u(t))A_u(t)c_u}{f_u(t)}, D_u^{edge}(t) = \frac{\alpha_u(t)A_u(t)c_u}{f_{u,s}(t)}$$

d. **Calculate total delay:**

$$D_u(t) = \max\{D_u^{loc}(t), D_u^{tx}(t) + D_u^{edge}(t)\}$$

e. **Compute energy consumption:**

$$E_u(t) = \kappa_u f_u^2(t) D_u^{loc}(t) + P_u(t) D_u^{tx}(t)$$

f. **Compute reward:**

$$r_t = - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} (d_u(t) D_u(t) + \lambda E_u(t))$$

g. **Update queues:**

$$Q_u(t+1) = \max[Q_u(t) - \mu_u(t), 0] + A_u(t)$$

h. **Store transition** in replay buffer:

$$\mathcal{D} \leftarrow (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})$$

i. **Sample minibatch** from \mathcal{D} and **update networks:**

5. **Critic target:**

$$y_i = r_i + \gamma Q_{\phi'}(s_{i+1}, \mu_{\theta'}(s_{i+1}))$$

6. **Critic loss:**

$$L(\phi) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (Q_\phi(s_i, a_i) - y_i)^2$$

Update ϕ using gradient descent

7. **Actor update** using deterministic policy gradient:

$$\nabla_{\theta} J \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \nabla_a Q_\phi(s_i, a) |_{a=\mu_\theta(s_i)} \nabla_{\theta} \mu_\theta(s_i)$$

j. **Soft update of target networks:**

$$\theta' \leftarrow \tau \theta + (1 - \tau) \theta', \phi' \leftarrow \tau \phi + (1 - \tau) \phi'$$

6. **Repeat** until all slots T are processed or policy converges.

7. **Return** learned actor $\mu_\theta(s)$ as the **offloading policy**.

Figure 4 Algorithm Process

3. Simulation Results

We have considered a smart city scenario, according to [6], where smart buildings and smart transportation exist and share a common edge infrastructure. A huge amount of computation-intensive tasks are produced by sensors, cameras, and energy management units, which are offloaded to edge sensors for real-time processing and energy optimization. Since collective edge infrastructure has been used by autonomous cars and smart buildings, it has led to a system limitation that multi-user task offloading under resource constraints, which has led to priority-based computation offloading. For example, in the case of smart transportation, high priority will be collision detection in which even a few milliseconds can lead to a severe accident. In the case of a smart building, the priority can vary from low to medium because they are less time critical, hence the edge server adopts a delay-aware mixed offloading, which allocates edge servers to high-priority task, while medium and low-priority tasks are queued and performed when edge resources are saturated.

The MIIoT environment is simulated using Python 3.6 and computed on a 13th Generation Intel Core i5 processor and NVIDIA® GeForce RTX™ 3050A, 16 GB RAM with Windows 11.

The dataset used for performance evaluation was derived through simulation, and with constraints values are as follows. 5 number of users is considered and distance between the MEC server and the user is within 200 m. The channel gain, which is the distance between MDs and the base station is 3. For intelligent offloading decision actor-critic method is considered for the baseline algorithm, which is DDQN and the proposed algorithm, which is PDPG, and prerequisites are mentioned in Table 3. For a medium priority task, partial offloading is considered, and the discount factor is 0.8. Behavioural analysis of baseline algorithm and proposed algorithm is compared on the basis of delay, priority, and offloading rate which are indicated as ordinate, the abscissa indicates low priority, medium priority, and high priority.

Table 3 Predefined values for Simulation

Notation	Parameter	Value
K	Number of users	5
D	Distance from MDs to MEC server	200m
N_0	Noise	174dbm/Hz
p_n	Transmission Power	500mW
P	Power of computing in MEC server	5GHz/s
T_i	Amount of task size	300kbits-500kbits

c_n	CPU cycles	900-1100 Megacycles
	Episodes	200
	Trade-off factor	0.99
	Seed of soft update of the target network	0.005

Parameter Setting

We will first evaluate the model behaviour based upon various parameters like batch sizes, memory size, and learning rates for proposed PSCO algorithm. For each parameter is tuned with three values are tuned and corresponding total rewards with respect to 300 episodes were observed. These values depicted how each parameter affects convergence speed, stability and overall efficiency for both algorithms, and which is best suited. The rewards are negative, which indicates that higher reward corresponds to better performance.

Figure 5 Proposed PSCO algorithm behaviour with different parameters like (a) batch sizes,(b) memory sizes (c) learning rate.

In Figure 5(a), batch sizes 32,64, and 128 are considered over 300 training episode, which indicate the efficient offloading and computation allocation decisions in MIoT environment. Initially batch size 32, increases gradually, as actor-critic adjusts quickly with new experience. But faster adaptation results in noisy updates due to higher variance in gradient estimates. Batch sizes of 64 and 128 slowly flatten and stabilize after episode 150 ,indicating convergence toward a near-optimal policy. We will consider 128 batch size to achieve better stability in MIoT environment.

In Figure 5(b), Memory sizes 1000,5000,and 10000 were considered for proposed PSCO algorithm over 300 training episodes. Initially, due to random exploration, there were low total rewards around -5000 .But gradually as the episode increased, the memory size 1000 showed faster improve,ment but later as the episode increased, its learning became unstable and converged to lower rewards. In contrast, memory sizes 5000-10000 demonstrate smoother and stable convergence ,as they provide richer and more varied training samples that improve critic estimation and actor updates. A 10,000 memory size achieves more stability and reduced variance.So, memory size is set to 10,000 for proposed PSCO algorithm .

In Figure 5(c), the Learning Rate Variation graph compares the convergence performance of the proposed algorithm under three different learning rates: 0.05, 0.01, and 0.005 over 300 training episodes. All configurations start with low total rewards (around -5000) due to random exploration during initial training, but the rewards steadily increase as the agent learns to make better offloading and resource allocation decisions. The model with a high learning rate (0.05) shows faster initial improvement but experiences mild fluctuations, indicating unstable gradient updates caused by overly aggressive parameter adjustments. In contrast, the low learning rate (0.005) ensures smooth and stable learning but converges more slowly, taking longer to reach optimal performance. The moderate learning rate (0.01) achieves the best overall performance it providing a balanced trade-off between convergence speed and stability, resulting in the highest final reward (around -900) with minimal oscillation. This demonstrates that a learning rate of 0.01 is optimal for the proposed PSCO algorithm, as it stabilizes actor-critic updates and ensures efficient convergence to an optimal offloading policy in the MIoT environment.

In opportunistic offloading, training stability and convergence are directly influenced by hyperparameters such as learning rates, replay buffer size, batch size, discount factor, and exploration noise. Providing these parameters beforehand is essential for understanding the learning curves and the performance trends presented in the impact results.

Impact Parameter

To determine the adaptability and scalability of the proposed PSCO algorithm under dynamic network conditions, the relationship between execution delay and bandwidth is observed in Figure 8. By examining performance under different transmission power levels, i.,e 80 dBm and 90dBm, the analysis highlights how variations in available communication

resources influence offloading efficiency and delay minimization in both priority-aware and non-priority conditions. It is observed that the execution delay exhibits a monotonic decrease with the increasing bandwidth across all configurations. This reduction is primarily attributed to the enhanced data transmission rate facilitated by higher bandwidth, which minimizes the time required for task offloading between MDs and edge servers. Consequently, larger bandwidth alleviates queuing latency and transmission congestion, thereby improving task completion efficiency.

Incorporating task priority in both algorithms has led to significant reduction in execution delay into resulting in better offloading decisions. For the baseline algorithm [11], incorporating task priority leads to a significant reduction in execution delay, particularly under limited bandwidth condition. At 80dBm, the proposed PSCO algorithm achieves approximately 18-22% lower delay than the baseline algorithm, while at 90dBm, the improvement reaches nearly 25% due to the combined effect of enhanced channel gain and adaptive decision-making. This improvement arises/is due to from priority-weighted experience replay ,which enables the agent to learn more efficiently from critical transitions and allocates bandwidth and computation resources toward high-priority tasks.

Overall performance of the proposed PSCO algorithm can be analysed in Figure 6 as The proposed algorithm 2 PSCO achieves the best adaptability and scalability under heterogeneous bandwidth and power conditions, validating its robustness and effectiveness in priority-sensitive and resource-constrained MEC environments.

Figure 6 Execution delay with respect to Bandwidth

The effectiveness of the baseline DDQN algorithm and the proposed algorithm PSCO in minimizing delay across multiple priority levels is depicted in Figure 7. As shown, the proposed PSCO algorithm outperforms the baseline DDQN algorithm for all priority categories. In case of high priority, the proposed PSCO algorithm achieves the lowest delay curve throughout training, resulting in high responsiveness in delay-sensitive applications. This is because of the priority-based queue sorting algorithm, which dynamically allocates transmission and computation resources based on weighted priority factors. At the end of training at episode 400, the high-priority delay under PSCO stabilizes around 0.10, whereas baseline DDQN algorithm converges near 0.15, signifying an overall 33% reduction in delay for the highest-priority tasks. At Episode 400, proposed PSCO algorithm reduces the latency for medium-priority tasks from baseline DDQN algorithm 0.20 to about 0.15, which is a 25% improvement. Though to a lesser degree, low-priority jobs also benefit: PSCO offers an approximately 18% reduction in delay, from roughly 0.22 (DDQN) to 0.18. Crucially, the steady ranking—high < medium < low—shows that proposed PSCO algorithm maintains rigorous QoS difference. While the quantifiable reductions demonstrate significant performance benefits in actual MEC situations, the smoother convergence of proposed PSCO algorithm curves suggests more robust learning dynamics.

Figure 7 Average Delay per Episode

Conclusion

This research presents a priority-based deep reinforcement learning framework for efficient computation offloading in multi-user Edge IoT environments. By integrating a Opportunistic Computation Offloading and PSCO algorithms, the system adaptively balances computation between local devices and MEC servers, minimizing delay and optimizing energy consumption under dynamic network conditions. Simulation outcomes demonstrate significant improvements in delay reduction, energy optimization, and resource utilization compared to baseline algorithms such as DDQN. The incorporation of task prioritization ensures that critical operations in industrial and vehicular systems are processed with minimal latency, leading to enhanced overall system reliability and Quality of Service (QoS).

In future work, the proposed framework can be extended by incorporating federated learning to enhance privacy-preserving distributed training across heterogeneous edge nodes. Additionally, the inclusion of multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) can enable cooperative decision-making among devices and servers, leading to better scalability and adaptability in large-scale IIoT systems. Furthermore, exploring energy harvesting and green edge computing strategies could make the system more sustainable and efficient. Finally, integrating real-world datasets and deploying the mechanism in actual smart city or industrial automation testbeds will further validate its practical applicability and robustness under realistic operating conditions.

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